

CFRP-STEEL HYBRIDS WITH IMPROVED AGEING RESISTANCE THROUGH ZINC OXIDE NANORODS - INVESTIGATION OF BASIC MECHANISMS

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ABSTRACT

An important aspect for the use of hybrid systems made of fibre-reinforced plastic and metal is a sufficient ageing resistance of the adhesive bond. For this reason, the present study introduces an innovative wet-chemical surface treatment of steel substrates, which causes the growth of zinc oxide nanorods. Objectives are the increase of sub-microscopic roughness and the reduction of redox activity. Both aspects are investigated by surface analytical methods. Furthermore, hybrid beam specimens are manufactured by co-cured bonding before they are subjected to corrosive environments and tested under mechanical bending load. It is found that the layer of zinc oxide nanorods enhances the ageing resistance of the adhesive bond.

1 INTRODUCTION

Reducing vehicle mass through lightweight design is of great interest to the automotive industry. This is due to the influence of weight on substantial vehicle characteristics. Since the mass is included as a factor in three of the four driving resistances, a weight reduction leads to an increase in efficiency and range. Additionally, the kinetic energy of a vehicle depends on its mass. The body structure must be able to absorb this energy in the event of a collision. For these reasons, carbon fibre-reinforced plastics (CFRP) with its high mechanical values and low density are increasingly used in modern car bodies. In particular, a local and load adapted reinforcement of metal components by CFRP offers weight-saving potential at moderate additional costs. Such hybrid systems are already in use in automobiles. An example is the B-pillar of the BMW 7 [1].

Bending loads on (asymmetrical) hybrid systems made of fibre-reinforced plastic and metal can result in diverse failure types depending on the composite materials, the laminate structure, the manufacturing conditions and the load characteristics. The failure modes of unidirectional (UD) layers of fibre-reinforced plastics correspond to fibre and / or inter-fibre fractures. Another type of failure in multi-layer composites is delamination. Due to their susceptibility to corrosion and ageing, hybrids can also delaminate at the polymer/metal interface. This indicates an insufficient (remaining) adhesion. In these cases, an appropriate surface pre-treatment of the metal substrate may be required to achieve a durable bond.

2 STATE OF THE ART

3.1 Ageing mechanisms of hybrids

Hybrid systems, e.g. in vehicle structures, are exposed to various loads over their service life. In addition to mechanical stress, important factors are moisture or water, elevated or freezing temperatures and media. The resistance of the solitaire materials and physical-chemical bonds at the polymer/metal interface determine the utilisability of a hybrid.

The degradation of the initial properties follows from a variety of ageing mechanisms. An important aspect with regard to polymers is the absorption or inclusion of water, which leads to a reduction of Young's modulus and glass transition temperature [2]. In a hybrid composite, physical-chemical bonds

between polymer molecules and metal oxides can also be weakened or eliminated by water [3]. Other damage mechanisms in the presence of an electrolyte are based on corrosion. Cathodic delamination includes the sub-processes metal dissolution (anodic area) and oxygen reduction (cathodic area). At the cathode, the reduction of oxygen produces hydroxides. This causes the transport of sodium cations to the delamination tip in order to compensate this charge. The electrolyte ingress leads to a progressive de-adhesion at the polymer/metal interface. The current circuit is closed by an electron exchange between anode and cathode [4]. In addition, corrosion can occur by galvanic action if two different materials are in contact. Studies show, that the electrical potential difference between steel and carbon fibres is sufficient to induce galvanic corrosion [5].

3.2 Surface treatment of substrates

To achieve a strong and age-resistant polymer/metal bond, numerous pre-treatments of metal substrates exist. According to their mode of action, common methods underlie mechanical (e.g. grit blasting), physical (e.g. laser structuring) or (electro) chemical mechanisms. Possible objectives of a pre-treatment are the cleaning of the metal surface, the modification of the surface morphology, the activation of the surface or the improvement of the wettability by the polymer. In this context, some authors denote that the nano-roughness of the substrate influences the durability of adhesive bonds [6].

The most common surface treatment for metal substrates is grit blasting. This process produces a clean, microscopic rough and chemically active surface by mechanical abrasion [7]. An innovative approach in the context of chemical surface modifications is the synthesis of zinc oxide (ZnO) nanorods. Contrary to grit blasting, such coatings can increase the surface roughness on a sub-microscopic level. Vayssieres et al. [8] carried out first experimental work on the synthesis of zinc oxide nanorods from aqueous solution for the deposition of crystalline and homogeneous layers. The coating process is characterised by high environmental compatibility and low costs. Although the electrical and optical properties of such zinc oxide layers have been examined extensively since, only a few studies address the mechanical effects of zinc oxide nanorods on metal/polymer joints. Ozcan et al. [9] have been successful in depositing nanorods on commercial galvanized steel surfaces, improving their corrosive behaviour and adhesion properties to epoxy resin.

3 EXPERIMENTAL

3.1 Materials

As composite material, unidirectional carbon fibres (50k, 300 g/m²) pre-impregnated with a fast-curing epoxy resin is used. In cured stage, the thickness of a single CFRP layer corresponds to 0.3 mm. The metal substrate is a dual-phase steel grade of type HCT 780 XD. On delivery condition, the galvanized (Z100) steel sheets exhibit a zinc thickness of 7 µm.

3.2 Methods

3.2.1 Synthesis of zinc oxide nanorods

The steel surfaces are pre-treated by wet-chemical dip-coating initiating the growth of zinc oxide nanorods. According to Ozcan et al. [9] and Ma et al. [10], an equimolar solution of zinc nitrate ($\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and hexamethylenetetramine ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4$) with a concentration of 0.1 M each is used for synthesis.

In a first step, contaminants on the substrate surface are removed by a three-stage cleaning process using ultrasonic baths of tetra hydro furan (THF), iso-propanol (IPA) and ethanol (EtOH) for 10 min each. The substrates are dried in a nitrogen stream afterwards. Secondly, the steel sheets are immersed in an alkaline solution of Ridosol (3 g/l) and Ridoline (30 g/l) for 30 s at 55 °C, rinsed with ultraclean water and dried by nitrogen. For the optional surface coating, the aqueous solutions of zinc nitrate and hexamethylenetetramine are separately heated to 95 °C and then merged in an unsealed reactor. Magnetic stirrers continuously circulate the solution during the isothermal coating process. After 30 minutes, the substrates are removed, rinsed with ultraclean water and dried in a nitrogen stream.

3.2.2 Scanning-Electron-Microscopy

In Scanning-Electron-Microscopy (SEM), electrons are focused on the surface, which interact with the electrons of the surface atoms. The depth resolution depends on the acceleration voltage between the emitting electrode and the conductive sample surface. Irradiation produces secondary and backscattered electrons, which are used for image generation. The scanning electron microscope used for this work is a type NEON®40 (Zeiss, Germany).

3.2.3 Atomic force microscopy

The surface topography is analysed by Atomic-Force-Microscopy (AFM). Here, a probe with a sharp tip (radius < 10 nm) is brought in close proximity to the specimen surface and moved relatively in a raster. Interactions between the probe tip and the surface lead to the deflection of the cantilever arm, which is detected by means of a laser beam and a photodetector. Measurements are made using a MFP-3D-SA (Asylum Research). Specifications of the cantilever are a force constant of 0.2 N/m and a resonance frequency of 13 kHz. The measurements are conducted in contact mode with at least 512 x 512 measuring points over a measuring area of 5 x 5 µm.

The surface is characterised based on the RMS (root-mean-squared) value as well as the surface enlargement factor $A_{\%}$. RMS results from the mean of the deviation squares while the $A_{\%}$ -factor corresponds to the quotient of measuring area and the sub-microscopic sample surface. The roughness values are averaged over five measurements each.

$$RMS = \sqrt{\frac{1}{MN} \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N (z(x_m, y_n) - (z_{average}))^2} \quad (1)$$

3.2.4 Cyclovoltammetry

The electrochemical behaviour of surfaces is determined by a setup of three electrodes. In cyclovoltammetry (CV) investigations, a characteristic current at the working electrode (sample) can be measured between the working electrode and the counter electrode by applying a voltage in the external current circuit. Polarization is performed with a constant feed rate between two defined potential limits. The obtained current-voltage diagrams provide information about electrode reactions (charge transfer and mass transport through the electrolyte to the electrode surface). For the cyclovoltammetry measurements, ten cycles are conducted in a potential range of 0.05 V to -0.35 V (vs. OCP) with a feed rate of 60 mV/s. A borate buffer (pH=8.3, without chloride) is used as electrolyte.

3.2.4 Manufacturing and ageing of hybrids

Hybrid test specimens are produced by co-cured bonding. In this process, layers of pre-impregnated fibres are stacked on the surface-modified steel substrates prior to consolidation and curing in a sealed mould cavity for 4 minutes. Here, a pressure of 0.3 MPa and a temperature of 150 °C is applied. Subsequently, hybrid specimens are coated with an epoxy-based varnish by cathodic electrophoresis and dried at 180 °C for 30 minutes.

The ageing of the samples is carried out under severe ambient conditions in a corrosion chamber. The ageing cycle corresponds to the consecutive application of salt spray with a NaCl concentration of 5 % (50 g/l) at 35 °C (4 h), ambient climate corresponding to 23 ± 2 °C (4 h) and wet and warm conditions with 95 % r.H. at 40 °C (16 h). Five repetitions of this cycle are followed by 48 h at 23 °C and a relative humidity of 50 %. The beam samples are stored under these corrosive environments for 2, 4 or 6 weeks prior to the mechanical tests.

3.2.5 Mechanical tests

Mechanical tests are carried out on hybrid beam specimens with dimensions of 80 x 15 mm. The hybrid specimens are composed of a steel substrate with a thickness of 1.8 mm and a bidirectional laminate of carbon fibre-reinforced plastic (figure 1, left). The surface of the metal substrate is alkaline cleaned and optionally coated with zinc oxide nanorods.

Figure 1: Hybrid beam specimens (left) and test setup (right).

The mechanical testing of beam samples is carried out by means of a three-point bending device under ambient temperature (AT), $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $+60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively. According to DIN EN ISO 14125, the support distance is 64 mm with a diameter of supports and pressure fin of 10 mm (figure 1, right). The force of the pressure fin is applied on the metal side of the specimen with a constant crosshead speed of 10 mm/min until failure initiation. For the test procedure, a universal testing machine type Criterion C45 (MTS) is used.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Surface characteristics

The surface properties are characterised by SEM, AFM and CV measurements. The visualization of the metal surface on a sub-microscopic level illustrates the modification of the surface morphology (figure 2). As a result of the synthesis, zinc oxide nanorods with a diameter of about 200 nm are present. These hexagonal rods are mostly disordered and form a closed layer.

Figure 2: Electron micrograph of an alkaline cleaned (left) and zinc oxide coated (right) steel surface.

The modification of surface roughness through the layer of zinc oxide nanorods is quantified by AFM measurements. In order to evaluate the nano-roughness, the surface measurement data are corrected for microscopic unevenness or waviness by a polynomial approach. Figure 3 shows a representative topography for both surfaces. The alkaline cleaned surface has a square mean roughness value of 1.7 nm and a surface enlargement factor of 0.2 %. The surface coated with zinc oxide shows a significant increase of surface roughness with a RMS value of 17.7 nm. This is linked to a surface enlargement of 7.5 % on average.

Figure 3: Topography of an alkaline cleaned (left) and zinc oxide coated substrate (right).

Figure 4 shows the cyclic voltammetry diagrams for both surface conditions. In case of the alkaline cleaned surface, two oxidation peaks occur at -0.99 V (pos. 1) and -1.07 V (pos. 2), respectively. Over the load cycles, these abscissa values remain approximately constant while the anodic partial current density increases from about $30 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ to $200 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ (pos. 1) or $20 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ to $150 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ (pos. 2). A reduction peak is first located at an abscissa value of -1.19 V with an incremental shift of about 20 mV in total. The anodic partial current density decreases from $-120 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ to about $-760 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$. The height of current densities give rise to the assumption that multi-electron transfer reactions occur. However, the zinc oxide coating significantly inhibits the transfer of electrons. The curve shape indicates capacitive surface behaviour caused by the reorganization of charges in the electrolyte towards the electrochemical double layer near the electrode surface.

Figure 4: Cyclic voltammetry of alkaline cleaned (left) and zinc oxide coated substrate (right).

4.2 Quasi-static bending tests on beam specimens

Bending tests are carried out under quasi-static test conditions on specimens that have been stored in the corrosion test for up to six weeks (W). Tests take place at ambient temperature (0, 2, 4, 6W) as well as -20 °C and $+60$ °C (0, 6W). Figure 5 shows representative force-displacement diagrams determined on hybrid specimens after two weeks of storage in the corrosion test. The onset and type of failure is denoted. The rhombus indicates a shear-induced delamination failure within the fibre-plastic composite that typically occurs between the outer 0° and 90° layer. This failure type is caused at a characteristic load value, which mainly depends on material properties and the laminate structure. It is observed for all specimens with zinc oxide interface, regardless of the duration of ageing and testing temperature. The second type of failure is induced by shear stresses in the polymer/metal interface. This failure occurs at lower bending forces and is marked by a triangle in the force-displacement diagram. It is only observed in case of hybrids with alkaline cleaned substrate surfaces. While this type of failure does not occur without prior ageing, it is existent in four out of six tests after six weeks under corrosive environments. In the case of a six-week ageing period and testing at -20 °C or $+60$ °C, this failure occurs at all tested specimens with alkaline cleaned metal surface.

Figure 5: Force-displacement diagrams of bending tests at ambient temperature for hybrid beam specimens with alkaline cleaned (left) and zinc oxide coated interface (right) after two weeks corrosion test.

Visual inspection of the interface reveals the cause of the increasing number of failures at the polymer/metal interface with ageing duration for hybrids with alkaline cleaned substrates. After six weeks of corrosion testing, the metal substrates show extensive corrosive damage emanating from both ends of the surface (figure 6).

Figure 6: Surface damage of an alkaline cleaned substrate with failure at the polymer/metal interface after six weeks storage in the corrosion test.

For the hybrid beams with zinc oxide interface, the test curves show a high reproducibility. With the given conditions, the failure load depends on the properties of the fibre-reinforced plastic and in particular on the matrix material. A comparison of the average breaking forces at ambient temperature indicates a slight increase due to ageing within the first four weeks. At the same time, the variation of this characteristic value increases. Ageing over a period of more than four weeks again leads to a reduction of the load at failure to the level without ageing. The highest or lowest failure loads occur under additional temperature influence. No ageing in combination with testing temperature of $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ results in the lowest average failure load overall. Storage in the corrosion test over a period of six weeks in combination with testing at $+60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ leads to the highest loads at failure initiation.

Figure 7: Average maximum forces at different ageing stages (0-6 weeks) and testing temperatures for hybrid specimens with zinc oxide substrate coating.

5 SUMMARY AND DISCUSSION

In the present work a wet-chemical deposition process for the surface treatment of steel substrates is presented in order to increase the adhesion and ageing resistance of hybrid systems composed of carbon fibre-reinforced plastic and steel. Basic mechanisms are investigated by topography and electrochemical analysis. Furthermore, hybrid beam samples are manufactured by means of co-cured bonding and exposed to corrosive environments prior to mechanical bending loads.

The wet-chemical surface treatment leads to a significant increase in sub-microscopic surface roughness, which is identified as an important factor for the ageing resistance of adhesive joints in literature. Cyclovoltammetry investigations indicate a fundamental change in the electrochemical behaviour of the metal surface. This results from the closed layer of zinc oxide which inhibits electron release and thus prevents cathodic and galvanic corrosion. Mechanical bending tests verify the influence of the surface modification on the durability of the polymer/metal interface compared to hybrid beams with alkaline cleaned substrates. Test specimens with zinc oxide surface modification exclusively fail due to shear stresses within the fibre-plastic composite. This failure is forwarded by inherent residual stresses between layers with 0° (longitudinal) and 90° (transversal) fibre orientation. In this context, the ageing over a period of six weeks has no negative effect on the failure load. Moderate water absorption can even be conducive by reducing residual stresses and plasticizing the resin. However, in case of hybrids with alkaline cleaned surface, failure at the polymer/metal interface is increasingly observed with ageing duration. This indicates an insufficient remaining adhesion of the adhesive joint due to corrosive damage at the polymer/metal interface. Based on these findings, the presented wet-chemical pre-treatment of steel substrates makes a promising contribution to the safe use of hybrid systems for structural applications even under corrosive load.

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